

Grant agreement no. 312788

**ORCID AND DATACITE
INTEROPERABILITY NETWORK**

www.odin-project.eu

**D1.3 First Periodic Report
WP1 – Project Management**

V2_0

Final

Abstract:

This first periodic report, as a contractual deliverable, describes at a high level the work that the ODIN consortium has carried out in the first year of the project, and an overview of the resources used in the project so far.

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	D1.3 First year report		
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1. PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

ODIN: ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network – <http://www.odin-project.eu>

Context

‘Data as infrastructure’ is a critical concept for a fully-integrated European Research Area (ERA) to drive innovation forward as envisaged by the Digital Agenda for Europe. The lack of data availability hinders this vision. In academic publishing, peer review and citation have long been recognised as mechanisms for endorsing the trustworthiness of research outputs and incentivizing researchers to contribute. Trustworthy research data will only be widely available if the same principles are applied.

Key, participative, initiatives have emerged to address this challenge. The DataCite consortium has assigned over 1.6 million DOI names in the last few years to make research data citable. The Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID) was launched in October 2012 and by the end of September 2013 has over 330,000 researchers and contributors registered. ORCID offers the opportunity to identify individual authors across systems and infrastructures, including scholarly works that can have up to thousands of authors (as in the case of the High-Energy Physics community). Researchers often change their affiliation, and collaborate across national disciplinary boundaries.

The ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network (ODIN), a project funded by the European Commission (FP7), aims to build on the success of DataCite and ORCID by designing an ‘awareness layer’ for persistent author and object identifiers, thereby reducing technical, cultural and logistical barriers to the accessibility, attribution and trust of data. Identifier awareness will make it possible to stabilise:

- References to a data object;
- Tracking of use and re-use;
- Links between a data object, subsets, articles, rights statements and every person involved in its life-cycle (creator, editor, reviewer, aggregator, etc.).

Given the importance of these functions as we approach HORIZON2020, we aim to: promote dialogue and awareness around author, data and rights identification and interoperability; provide a vision around persistent identifier (PID) interoperability; concretely define and address key interoperability principles; analyse these principles within extreme cases in different disciplines, analyse gaps in current infrastructure provision that hinder interoperability and outline key actions necessary to promote future PID interoperability in the scientific data domain in Europe and globally.

The ODIN project is coordinated by The British Library and the ODIN consortium is formed by The British Library, CERN, DataCite, ORCID EU, The Australian National Data Service, arXiv and Dryad.

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Work performed during the first Year

For work package (WP) 2, communication, and the project as a whole, the period began with the successful planning and staging of the kick-off event. A comprehensive set of speakers were selected to represent all the relevant stakeholders (e-infrastructure providers, libraries, publishers, 3rd party services using PIDs). The topics of discussion were carefully planned with these experts in advance to the meeting.

In parallel a communications plan was produced to provide a strategic framework for the project to communicate effectively and efficiently with stakeholders. One of the key elements in communicating ODIN's findings and events to the relevant audiences and communities was the development of the project website; the website is dynamic and is regularly updated. The ODIN Codesprint and 1st Year Conference events were also planned during the first year.

In work package 3, proofs of concept, work was carried out on the first phase in developing two disciplinary proofs of concept using interoperable, persistent identifiers in Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS) and High Energy Physics (HEP). These proofs of concept used desk research and input from key partner organisations and were developed in partnership with the international partners: the Australian Data Archive on behalf of ANDS for HSS and arXiv for HEP.

In work package 4, interoperability, the conceptual model of the interoperability framework between open identifiers for data and contributors in different infrastructures has been completed. This work was carried out in partnership with the extra-European partner, Dryad and through consultation included validation from organisations not directly involved in the project.

Work package 5, strategy, completed a detailed assessment of the gaps that hinder the implementation of the "thin layer" of interoperable, open, persistent identifiers. This process started with the input of the kick-off meeting and carried on with input from the consortium and importantly from the wider community. In parallel a draft roadmap was produced, which includes recommendations for addressing and closing the gaps. This leveraged the establishment within the project of a network of external expertise and connections to relevant stakeholders.

All results from the project were put through an international validation by the extra-European partners as part of Work Package 6.

Main results

The kick-off meeting provided a comprehensive overview of the current persistent identifier landscape, as well as valuable input from key stakeholders external to the project. Eleven presenters from a variety of stakeholder groups provided important perspectives, and the extensive discussion by all meeting participants further elaborated on key points. Based on the key scientific inputs, the following actions were identified:

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- i) Encourage discussion and collaboration between communities
- ii) Address specific issues of working with large numbers of small heterogeneous datasets
- iii) Identify main interoperability use cases and define their business value
- iv) Encourage development of novel tools to track the reuse of data

The event is summarised in **D2.2 Kick off Report**.

Two disciplinary proofs of concept reports have been produced. **D3.1 Humanities and Social Science (HSS) Proof of Concept** investigates the needs of Humanities and Social Science researchers through examining the use and re-use of British Birth Cohort Studies. This report contains the discipline context and characteristics associated with this research area, it outlines the current state of unique and persistent identifier adoption and use and outlines preliminary workflows to build on the opportunities that exist in this area. **D3.2 High Energy Physics (HEP) Proof of Concept** investigates the needs of High-Energy Physics researchers by using the data exchange between INSPIRE¹, arXiv and HepData² as a case study. This report provides a study of the community requests and the preliminary models to cover them, outlining the development of a proof of concept during the 2nd year. The HEP proof of concept has led to the recent integration of ORCID into the INSPIRE platform.

Interoperability results have been published in **D4.1 Conceptual Model of Interoperability**. The model describes key criteria for persistent identifiers and metadata and explores the relationship between different identifier schemes. The report also describes how this conceptual model fits into the Linked Open Data (LOD) model and outlines several key relevant workflows. Outside of project resources partners have also leveraged on the knowledge developed in the interoperability work package to create a new service that proves interoperability between identifiers in a technical sense. This service allows users to search and claiming works in DataCite under an ORCID identifier and has helped to validate the vision of ODIN.

D5.1 Gap Analysis and Roadmap provides a study of the strengths and weaknesses of the current implementation and handling of PIDs across disciplines and stakeholder groups. It is summarized in stakeholder specific SWOT analyses. The concise gap analysis highlights main areas that need to be addressed and puts particular emphasis to the opportunities ahead – the potential that can be unlocked by an open and interoperable PID framework in Europe and beyond.

The ODIN approach has been examined and validated from an international perspective in **D6.1 International Validation of D3.1, D3.2, D4.1 and D5.1**. This report presents the feedback of the Australian and US partners on the ODIN deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D4.1 and D5.1.

¹ <http://inspirehep.net/>

² <http://hepdata.cedar.ac.uk/>

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The 1st year ended with the Codesprint and 1st Year Conference. In the Codesprint around 20 participants practically applied the interoperability principles explored by ODIN, such as adding value by connecting identifiers and associated information using open APIs, the outcomes of the Codesprint were shared with the community at the first year event. The conference included presentation of the results from ODIN's first year and then presentations from organisations outside the project on complementary points of view, experiences and challenges in disciplines beyond ODIN and value added services that can be built on identifier infrastructure. The Codesprint and 1st Year Conference are reported on in **D2.3 First year communication report including results from first year event.**

Eleven deliverables were submitted to the European Commission during the first period of the project, as stipulated in the Description of Work. All public deliverables can be found at <http://odin-project.eu/project-outputs/>

Future Work

For each work package, the key planned activity is described below.

In WP2, communications, activities will carry on focusing on engaging with the relevant communities. These activities will culminate in staging ODIN's final event, which is scheduled to take place in M23 at the British Library in London. This event will present the ODIN roadmap and the mature proofs of concept. The event will bring together the project's communities of interest. A particular focus for the second year conference will be the sustainability of the 'thin layer', and the conference will showcase prototypes of both existing and newly developed tools using the DataCite and ORCID APIs

In WP3, proofs of concept, work is on-going on the two disciplinary proofs of concept and in the second year activity will be focused on turning the preliminary models into robust workflows that can be implemented in collaboration with partners in the community. The current focus for the proofs of concept is on exploring commonalities from the two disciplines to create a common global picture. This process will draw on the work carried out in the disciplines, the framework created by the conceptual model of interoperability and the suitability and compatibility of practical applications explored during the ODIN Codesprint. Attention will be paid to input from disciplines and communities not represented in the project, as gathered during the first-year event and through the contacts established then and through the WP4 and WP5 activities.

In WP4, interoperability, the framework developed in the conceptual model of interoperability will be further developed into concrete examples in partnership with DataCite and ORCID members. A generic specification will be developed to provide interoperability of the APIs for ORCID and DataCite and their constituencies at the data centre and institutional level, These specifications shall be tested in prototype tools implemented in the existing DataCite and ORCID services.

Conceptual models for interoperability of different resource identifiers will be further refined by cooperation between DataCite and the European Persistent Identifiers

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Consortium (EPIC)³. These models will be based on the work of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) working groups on “PID information types” and “data citation” in which DataCite is actively taking part.

In WP5 a refinement of the draft roadmap (as presented in D5.1) will take place in the second year of ODIN. It is needed to engage multiple disciplines, as well as the wide set of stakeholders involved in scholarly communication. A first, crucial step for the progress of the second year has already been achieved with the 1st year event (Oct 17th at CERN). A number of key stakeholders involved in PID have been invited to report on their current work, gaps and visions. The event showed that the gaps and challenges appear to be rather similar across disciplines and stakeholder groups involved. During the second year, it will be needed to build on this consensus and agree on possible common solutions. This results in a conceptual framework on which e-infrastructure services can be built. In practice, this requires more outreach and engagement with the relevant stakeholder groups from research communities, e-infrastructure providers, publishers, 3rd party services and libraries.

The extra-European partners will continue their role in providing an international perspective and input into all aspects project work in the second year and will validate the project outputs. Further validation will be provided at the high profile second year event. The event will bring together the relevant stakeholder groups from research communities, e-infrastructure providers, publishers, 3rd party services and libraries. A particular focus for the second year conference will be the sustainability of the ‘thin layer’, and the conference will showcase prototypes of tools using the DataCite and ORCID programming interfaces for attribution and evaluation.

Planned project tasks and activities will also take note of the changing and maturing environment that ODIN operates in. At the start of ODIN ORCID had not even launched and the ODIN kick-off was timed alongside the ORCID launch. ORCID has matured and is working with its community to understand its users, their motivations and how they use the identifiers. In the last year DataCite has grown and is working with its community to understand lessons learnt from it’s first few years of operation. The RDA gathered pace and ODIN aims to highlight issues around identifiers in its working and interest groups. Finally the EC’s plans around Horizon 2020 are becoming clear and ODIN will strive to deliver relevant information for its implementation.

³ <http://www.pidconsortium.eu/>

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2. PROJECT OBJECTIVES, WORK PROGRESS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

2.1. Project objectives for the period

The ODIN Project identified four specific objectives:

- Access
- Discovery
- Interoperability
- Sustainability

We present details for each of those objectives and the corresponding achievements to date.

2.1.1. Access

“Researchers must be able to seamlessly access datasets used in a journal article, a grant report, or another scholarly artefact, with explicit and unambiguous terms of use.”⁴

ODIN objective: Build shared understanding

“The project will engage with all ODIN stakeholder communities to understand how gaps in the support for data and contributor identifiers may be bridged, in order to meet the needs of the community for access to research data. Consensus will be built on a road-map to implement the missing identifier layer, and overcome the access challenge. This will be subject to a thorough validation, and fully-supported by all stakeholders, with concrete recommendations feeding into HORIZON2020.”⁵

ODIN held a successful kick-off event where a comprehensive set of speakers were selected to represent all the relevant stakeholders in the community (e-infrastructure providers, libraries, publishers, 3rd party services using PIDs). Speakers and participants contributed their thoughts and ideas on the current identifier landscape and what needed to be done to encourage adoption and interoperability. This event validated the project’s aims and objectives and led to consensus about what needs to be achieved. This consensus was built around the need to encourage discussion and collaboration between communities, address specific issues of working with large numbers of small heterogeneous datasets, identify main interoperability use cases and define their business value and to encourage development of novel tools to track the reuse of data.

Engagement with community stakeholders has continued through communications activities by each partner. In addition a consultation process was carried out for WP4, interoperability, and WP5, strategy, where additional feedback was received. This

⁴ ODIN Description of Work

⁵ ODIN Description of Work

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consultation throughout the year has been an iterative process which has helped the project to gain the input of many external voices and to avoid silo developments and foster a common vision amongst the community. D4.1 (Conceptual model of interoperability) and D5.1 (Gap analysis and Roadmap), were validated by external experts not involved directly in the project. WP5 also carried out a number of interviews with experts. The interviews took place face to face during an international conference in Oxford (the ORCID Outreach Meeting, Symposium on Research Attribution in May 2013 in Oxford, UK). This step validated the first gap analysis, and allowed relevant stakeholders in the community (e-infrastructure providers, libraries, publishers, 3rd party services using PIDs) to identify where they saw gaps and inform the specifications of the draft roadmap. The 1st year event which was attended representatives of the relevant stakeholder groups helped to build a shared understanding of current gaps and a possible common vision for the future. This consultation process will continue during the second year and further collaborations with relevant partner projects and stakeholders will inform a broader, but detailed roadmap which is supported by all relevant communities.

2.1.2. Discovery

“Researchers must be able to identify scholarly works or datasets related to each other either through networks of references and citation or through shared contributors”⁶

ODIN objective: explore proofs of concept

The project has analysed two very different disciplines:

- **Humanities and Social Sciences (HSS):** *“where generators, curators and users of multiple datasets are separated by considerable distances in space and/or in time, without any prevailing framework for identification of the data or the different contributors.”*
- **High Energy Physics (HEP):** *“where massively multi-authored publications and their accompanying datasets exist in multiple versions across several repositories, with no mechanism currently in place to aggregate them.”⁷*

The ability to discover, navigate and represent the association between datasets and contributors was achieved for the first time in these fields. The commonalities and lessons learnt, will feed into the ways in which we address the other challenges during the second year.

The main goal of this period was to develop disciplinary proofs of concept for open and interoperable persistent identifiers of data and contributors in scholarly communication. In particular, the focus was on proving the ability to navigate across data and contributors in the area of High-Energy Physics (HEP) and Humanities and Social

⁶ ODIN Description of Work

⁷ ODIN Description of Work

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Sciences (HSS) and to start to explore commonalities with each other as well as other knowledge areas.

The process of designing the models and building the proof of concepts started after the kick-off meeting and was successfully achieved, thanks to participation of the key stakeholders in each discipline.

2.1.3. Interoperability

“Users must be able to connect datasets and contributors across independent platforms using different, but interoperable identifier schemes.”⁸

ODIN objective: demonstrate interoperability

“ODIN will define concrete interoperability solutions between ORCID and DataCite identifiers so that data in a selected system participating in DataCite can be connected (through DataCite and ORCID) to contributors identified in another system, and vice versa.”⁹

As a first step, ODIN partners identified different use cases of interoperability between data and author identifiers. These use cases were used as the foundation of the conceptual model of interoperability. ODIN designed concrete interoperability solutions between ORCID and DataCite so that information identified in their respective systems could be connected between them. Outside of project resources additional effort resulted in the beta launch of a new service for searching and claiming works in DataCite under an ORCID identifier. The tool is available at: <http://datacite.labs.orcid-eu.org>. In addition to this other practical applications testing and validating the principles behind interoperability were developed at the ODIN Codesprint.

2.1.4. Sustainability

“Funding agencies and research institutions must be able to depend on the on-going viability of the systems that provide and maintain persistent identifiers. The organisations that deliver those services may be commercial or non-profit, but in either case their sustainability depends on the value of the services they provide.”

ODIN objective: stimulate added-value services

“There are enormous opportunities for the providers of identifiers, and for innovative third parties, to provide value-added services on top of a layer of interoperable data and contributor identifiers.”

ODIN has already engaged with existing providers of products and services within the e-Science domain, ranging in scale from individual developers to large corporations. In

⁸ ODIN Description of Work

⁹ ODIN Description of Work

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it's first year ODIN has explored potential scenarios for exploitation of unique attribution, such as evaluation of the impact of datasets associated with specific contributors. This has been discussed in more detail during the interviews with experts within WP5. These interviews and further engagement with the stakeholders during the first year highlighted the need for coherent PID implementation on which 3rd party providers could build. Within WP4 some concrete examples have been already developed, specifically a tool to search and claim datasets. Additional tools were sketched during the ODIN Codesprint held in Geneva, prior to the first year conference. Stakeholders agree that such services are needed to enable Open Science practices in a seamless way without putting any burden on the researchers. The project will continue working on the outcome during the second year.

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2.2. Work progress and achievements during the period

2.2.1. WP2 – Communication

Summary of progress towards objectives and details for each task/significant results

The main objective of WP2 is to offer a communication framework within and beyond the ODIN Consortium in order to ensure representation of all stakeholder groups in the activities of the project.

During the first twelve months of the project we have communicated to stakeholder communities various information on published project outputs, upcoming events and other activity.

Activities by task

Task 2.2: Communication and dissemination, M1 – M23 (ORCID EU, DataCite, all)

The Communication plan was put into place. The project website was also set up at (www.odin-project.eu) and is being updated on a regular basis. ODIN partners have constantly been identifying and communicating with the different communities of interest for the project both online and in person. Table 1, below, shows some of the events that ODIN partners have participated in. Deliverable D2.1 (Kick-off preparation, Communication plan and Website) was produced and sent to the EC.

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Table 1 - ODIN Presentations and Talks at non-ODIN Events

Event title	Date	Partner	Location
Cohort and Longitudinal Studies Enhancement Resource (CLOSER) Leadership Team	29/11/2012	BL	London, UK
British Library Scholarship and Collections Open House	24/1/2013	BL	London, UK
Identity Awareness: Toward an Invisible e-Infrastructure for Identifying Data and Authors	28/10/2012	ANDS	Sydney, Australia
3ª Conferencia sobre calidad de revistas de ciencias sociales y humanidades (CRECS 2013)	9/5/2013	DataCite	Sevilla, Spain
FESABID 2013: XIII Jornadas Españolas de Documentación	25/5/2013	DataCite	Toledo, Spain
DataONE User Group	7/7/2013	Dryad	Chapel Hill, NC, USA
17th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries	22-26/9/2013	CERN	Velletta, Malta
ORCID Outreach Meeting	23/5/2013	ORCID	Oxford, UK
International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology (IASSIST) 2013	29/5/2013	BL, DataCite, Dryad, ORCID	Cologne, Germany
British Library DataCite Workshop no. 6: Research data metrics for impact and citation	14/6/2013	BL	London, UK
Association of Librarians in Social Sciences Summer Conference	30/7/2013	BL	London, UK
DataCite summer meeting 2013	19/09/2013	BL	Washington DC, USA
DataCite summer meeting 2013	20/09/2013	CERN, DataCite, ORCID	Washington DC, USA
Max Planck PubMan Days	24/10/2013	DataCite	Munich, Germany

ODIN has completed the following activities as laid out in the Communication plan (see D2.1 Kick-off preparation, Communication plan and Website):

- Launched a project website at <http://odin-project.eu>
- Published several blog posts on the website to announce availability of deliverables, upcoming ODIN events and more
- Announced the launch of the beta tool to claim datasets under ORCID iDs
- Announced the celebration of the Codesprint and first year conference
- Communicated the above to target audiences as appropriate (E-mail lists, Twitter etc.) via individual ODIN partners
- Published the scientific deliverables in advance of the First Year Event.

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Task 2.3: Planning and management of “big bang”, M3 – M11 (ORCID EU, CERN, all)

The first year conference was initially scheduled for month 11 (August 2013), but this was rescheduled for month 14 (15-17 October 2013) due to fears of low attendance during the European summer. These dates were agreed with the Project Officer. CERN, in cooperation with ORCID EU, took the lead in preparing a list of potential participants to invite, potential key areas to work on and other preparation work.

Dates for the event were announced via the event page on the website (see <http://odin-project.eu/events/1st-year-big-bang-and-codesprint/>), blog posts, and also communicated more widely by partners via Twitter and other channels as noted above. Additional event promotion took place as we drew closer to the event and (for example) agenda information was made available for communicating to potential participants. The participation of several ODIN partners to the ORCID Outreach Meeting, Symposium on Research Attribution, and the ORCID Codefest, in May 2013 in Oxford UK allowed us to identify potential candidates for the participation in the ODIN Codesprint.

Task 2.4: Hackathon outreach, M11 – M23 (ORCID EU, all)

The 1st year ODIN Codesprint was held at CERN Oct 15-16. Around 20 persons participated, roughly half of whom came from ODIN partner organizations not directly involved in the project. Among the external experts were the two winners of the ORCID Codefest “best project” competition, held in May 2013. As a reward for their work in Oxford, their costs for travelling to and staying at the event at CERN were covered by ODIN.

Out of an initial list of 10 project ideas, the Codesprint participants selected four to work on over the day and a half duration, organized in groups of 3 to 5 peoples. Results from the 4 projects were then summarized in the final session of the 1st year Conference on October 17th. The effort by the participants in the Codesprint has led to developing four new codebases that leverage the existing work by the ODIN partners. The new codebase enables the following functionalities:

- Embedding all my ORCID-claimed works (including data) on a webpage
- ODIN’s HAMR (Human/Authority Metadata Reconciliation) that demonstrates how a data centre can retrieve ORCIDs associated with DOIs in their own systems and populate their own metadata with authors and ORCIDs.
- ORCID UNION for data that can enables the links between an ORCID and a person’s works across multiple sources
- DataCite metadata entry form with ORCID support that is enabled by ANDS and DataCite automated services. A full report from the Codesprint will be included in an upcoming deliverable D2.3 (First year communication report including results from first year event).

Deviations from DoW/ impact on other tasks

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D2.1 (Kick off preparation, Communication plan and Website) and D2.2 (Kick off report) were delivered with marginal delay due to longer-than-expected lead time to hire ORCID EU staff, who joined in October 2013. This has had no impact on other contracted deliverables. The re-scheduling of the first-year event implies that D2.3 (First year communication report including results from first year event) was submitted in M14 with the Project Officer's agreement.

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final

Use of resources (including actual vs. planned)

Table 2: WP2 person-months per partner compared with the DoW.

No.	Short name	PM expected to be spent during the first 12 months of the project	PM spent in WP2
1	ANDS	0.0	0.0
2	arXiv	0.0	0.0
3	BL	0.5	0.4
4	CERN	1.5	1.9
5	DataCite	2.0	0.5
6	DRYAD	0.0	0.0
7	ORCID	6.5	7.2
TOTAL		10.5	9.9

Table 2 shows DataCite expended less effort than anticipated on outreach in the first year. This was due to a delay in staff being in place and focusing attention on developing WP4. DataCite will use WP4 results in the 2nd year to engage more with the community.

There is a difference between BL's half year effort reported D1.2 Interim Scientific Report and the final figures in this table. The figure in D1.2 was 1.1 person months and the final figure was 0.4 person months. This is due to an administrative error in D1.2, which has been rectified in this report. The error flagged 2 ORCID staff as BL staff for one month and gave the BL 0.88 additional person months that have now been transferred back into ORCID's total..

2.2.2. WP3 – Proofs of Concept

Summary of progress towards objectives and details for each task/significant results

The main objective of WP3, as per Annex 1 is to develop two disciplinary proofs of concept for open and interoperable persistent identifiers of data and contributors in scholarly communication, in a variety of current and future scenarios.

After input from the kick-off meeting, preliminary models and workflows have been created for the proofs of concept in both HSS and HEP. The results of the proofs of concept work have been published in two deliverables: D3.1 HSS Proof of Concept and D3.2 HEP proof of concept.

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final

Activities by task

Task 3.1 Common kick-off, M1 – M2 (BL, CERN, DataCite)

In order to obtain the widest perspectives, external stakeholders were invited to the kick-off meeting. Regarding the WP3 point of view, their input provided valuable insights to start creating the proofs of concepts.

For the HSS proof of concept, the meeting provided many useful insights from a wide range of stakeholders. Of particular relevance was the input of GESIS¹⁰, SSRN¹¹, JISC¹² and UK REPOSITORYNET+¹³. GESIS explained how they use DataCite DOIs for datasets in German economic and social collections, with many commonalities shared with the approach by UK Data Service in the UK. SSRN highlighted the need to show the benefits of sharing research data to the social science community and gave useful inputs from a US perspective. JISC's input was very useful for this work package as it allowed us to see their current thinking around name and object identifiers which will help us to make choices in the development of the conceptual model and inform workflows from a UK perspective.

JISC also expressed interest in engaging with the ODIN project because working with names and objects bridges 2 different areas of work for them (name identifiers and research data management). It was also useful to hear about the work of UK REPOSITORYNET+ as many of the objects relevant to the HSS proof of concept are held in UK repositories.

For the HEP proof of concept, the kick-off meeting provided invaluable input from different stakeholders and scenarios, allowing the opportunity to compare issues, needs and workflows, such as the data versioning solutions presented by GESIS or the Scopus integration with the ORCID website. This cross-disciplinary view applies directly to the design of the proof of concept, where the distinctive features of HEP have clear similarities with other areas, such as dataset versioning in the social sciences, increasing amounts of data sent to publishers and difficulties in disambiguating authors, counting citations, etc. This situation offers an opportunity to lead the way towards the adaptation and unification of workflows, as is a necessary basis for the clearly demanded interoperability of systems.

¹⁰ <http://www.gesis.org/en/institute/>

¹¹ <http://www.ssrn.com/>

¹² <http://www.jisc.ac.uk/>

¹³ <http://www.repositorynet.ac.uk/>

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
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Task 3.2 HSS. M2 – M23 (BL), First phase M2-M11

As part of this task a conceptual model around the use and re-use of British Birth Cohort Studies datasets was created. In the first year, preliminary workflows for the conceptual model for data providers using ORCID and DataCite have been designed. All available metadata and identifiers for the proof of concept areas were collected examined and linked together in the ODIN-discover tool (<http://odin-discover.eu/>) This process highlighted the gaps and issues that would hinder HSS participation in an open and interoperable identifier system and a number of challenges have been identified.

Datasets in the proof of concept are affected by different policies; for example, surveys hosted by the UK Data Service have DataCite DOIs and open metadata, whereas surveys funded by the Medical Research Council (MRC) do not use DataCite DOIs and access to metadata requires approval. We have opened up a dialogue with the MRC study, The National Survey for Health and Development to work with them to publish metadata and datasets with DOIs and to create and implement concrete workflows for assigning PIDs for people and research objects. We have found that quality of metadata concerning data creation and curation roles is variable and we have identified ways to improve this and will implement this in the second year.

Through data collection for the model, we have successfully made links between some surveys and datasets and different types of publication (published journals, working papers, grey literature etc.). This functionality is essential in order to track the impact of data resources. However we have identified issues in current data citation practices that means that the work carried out is not currently scalable to a discipline level. In the second year we plan to work with the GESIS data centre to explore new automated solutions for recognising data citations that they have developed for German Birth Cohort Studies.

In M9 a representative from the Australian Data Archive visited the BL for three weeks. During this time he provided invaluable input into the conceptual model and was involved in discussions with data creation and curation partners involved in the proof of concept. This visit coincided with an ODIN session on identifiers at the International Association for Social Science Information Service and Technology (IASSIST 2013) conference. This session provoked discussion with international data centres about ODIN's approach in relation to social science data centres globally and valuable feedback on the models and workflows was obtained. This international perspective showed us many commonalities in approach, systems and processes across national social science data centres, which will make the concrete workflows developed in year two relevant across the world

Task 3.3 HEP M3 – M23 (CERN, DataCite), First phase M2-M11

During the first phase, a set of conceptual models covering the particularities of the High-Energy Physics (HEP) field has been designed.

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	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final

Scholarly communication in HEP needs to deal with the “hyperauthorship” phenomenon: thousands of scientists signing together their publications. Such phenomenon has extended to datasets, where big collaborations run experiments and generate data.

This data, with different levels of abstraction, lives in separate, large-scale data centres. As the community involved considers its re-use as a key principle in scientific research, the implementation of interoperable and open workflows for data exchange becomes a need.

Persistent and shared identifiers for both data and authors are mandatory to facilitate access and data exchange among the different data centres, as currently each system uses its own internal identifiers.

INSPIRE, HepData and arXiv have developed the first steps for a proof of concept of such exchange workflows. During month 7, a member of the arXiv team visited CERN to provide input and share systems needs. As a result of the visit, an initial draft for the communication between arXiv and INSPIRE was written. Both systems stated the different identifiers used and committed to base the data exchange in shared ORCID's for authors and DOIs for objects.

In parallel, INSPIRE has developed support for ORCID's and DOIs and has started assigning the first DOIs for datasets from HepData, so the exchange between the three datacentres become possible during the next phase of the task.

Version management remains as a challenge for the second phase, as the important differences encountered between the systems will require further effort to overcome the difficulties.

Task 3.4 Common validation and review of first phase M11-M12 (BL, CERN)

The initial steps of the two disciplinary proofs of concept have been validated in two different ways.

The deliverables D3.1 and 3.2 were reviewed and validated by international partners in D6.1 and all reports were circulated prior to the first year event. Then, during it, key results were presented, including short demonstrations of the practical implementation of persistent identifiers among the proof of concept systems. The discussion sessions served to compare and validate the steps followed by the proofs of concept, certainly aligned with the needs and developments of the different stakeholders.

The validation in the practical hands-on level came during the Codesprint. The team members discussed project ideas and concepts with participants to see if these would be relevant and could be implemented in their discipline areas and whether tools developed would satisfy the needs of stakeholders. Then, different examples were built on top of the systems proposed by the project members and the ideas, needs and requests of the different participants. Four successful projects were developed,

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illustrating the reduction of the gap and the simplification of the procedures by using persistent identifiers and common workflows.

Deviations from DoW/ impact on other tasks

None have been observed.

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
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Use of resources (including actual vs. planned)

Table 3 WP3 person-months per partner compared with the DoW.

No.	Short name	PM expected to be spent during the first 12 months of the project	PM spent in WP3
1	ANDS	0.0	0.0
2	arXiv	0.0	0.0
3	BL	4.0	11.7
4	CERN	4.0	19.2
5	DataCite	2.0	0.2
6	DRYAD	0.0	0.0
7	ORCID	0.0	0.0
TOTAL		10.0	31.1

Table 3 shows BL has dedicated more effort than planned in this initial phase of the project in order to establish the links with all stakeholders in the field and to plan practical implementations of ODIN concepts in year 2 which will lead to the development of robust and concrete workflows. Additional effort over BL's total allocation is not being funded from the ODIN budget.

CERN has allocated its own additional resources beyond the project funding envelope to the proof-of-concept, with a junior software engineer working at the interface between the design of the proof of concept and the INSPIRE digital library platform.

DataCite has expended less effort than originally budgeted on this work package. This was due to spending the majority of person months on developing a mature conceptual model of interoperability in WP4.

As there was unfunded activity within this work package partners will resource at a minimum the remaining expected (budgeted) funded person months in year 2.

2.2.3. WP4 – Interoperability

Summary of progress towards objectives and details for each task/significant results

The main objective of this WP is to prove the value of achieving interoperability between open identifiers for data and contributors in different infrastructures.

ORCID and DataCite have been working during the first twelve months of the project examining the current state-of-the-art in identifier systems, discussing the needs and challenges for identifier interoperability with different stakeholders, and developing a conceptual model of interoperability.

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final

Activities by task

Task 4.1 Preparation for Kick-Off, M1 – M2 (DataCite, ORCID EU)

The scope of WP4, interoperability, is to prove the value of achieving interoperability between open identifiers for data and contributors in different infrastructures. At day one of the kick-off event we received especially valuable inputs on this issue from two external participants: OKKAM¹⁴ which represented the EC-funded DIGOIDUNA study¹⁵ on the role of identifiers for digital objects and authors and are ODIN subcontractors; and OCLC¹⁶ which represented the International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI)¹⁷ initiative. These inputs were included in the first WP4 deliverable: "Conceptual model of interoperability" submitted in August 2013.

Task 4.2 Conceptual Model, M3 – M8 (DataCite, ORCID EU, all)

In joint meetings, DataCite and ORCID identified two important use cases of interoperability between data and author identifiers: submission of datasets to the data center, and claiming of already published datasets in the ORCID registry.

These use cases were used as the foundation of the work on deliverable D4.1, describing the conceptual model of interoperability. The conceptual model defines how these identifiers can successfully and openly interoperate inside each of the individual targeted infrastructures and suggest open avenues for their mutual integration. The deliverable was subject to an open consultation process with external experts along with D5.1.

DataCite organised a meeting with representatives from the EPIC consortium that offer a handle-based data identification infrastructure. Based on this meeting the developers of DataCite and EPIC have discussed the technical concepts of identifier interoperability and methods of mapping one identifier to the other. Use-cases were defined to describe how different identifiers can be used for data in different parts of the research lifecycle and how they can evolve into each other.

¹⁴ <http://www.okkam.org/>

¹⁵ DIGOIDUNA. Digital Object Identifiers and Unique Authors Identifiers to Enable Services for Data Quality Assessment, Provenance and Access. Report for Experts Feedback. Università degli Studi di Trento: 2011. Available at: http://namesproject.files.wordpress.com/2011/12/digoiduna_final_report_expert_feedback.pdf

¹⁶ <http://www.oclc.org/>

¹⁷ <http://www.isni.org/>

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As a result of the discussion GWDG (Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen), the technical administrators of the EPIC consortium joined DataCite as an affiliated member in September 2013 to strengthen their relationship and promote further identifier interoperability.

ORCID EU has worked with ISNI (<http://www.isni.org>) with the aim for interoperation through linking and sharing of public data between the two systems. In addition, ORCID and ISNI are committed to investigate the feasibility of a shared identifier scheme for a single number to represent an individual in both the ORCID and ISNI databases.

During M9 a selected expert from Dryad visited ORCID and DataCite to provide technical input into describing the conceptual model of interoperability.

Task 4.3 Hackathon Preparation M8 – M11 (ORCID EU, DataCite)

Both ORCID and DataCite technical personnel worked actively both in the planning of and participation in the Codesprint held in October in Geneva, together with experts and developers in the field of scholarly communication and related services.

Task 4.4 Validation M11 – M12 (DataCite, ORCID EU, all)

The conceptual model was validated in two complementary ways as planned in the DoW. Technical experts used both the DataCite and the ORCID APIs during the Codesprint for developing some potential added-value services.

The main outcome of WP4, deliverable D4.1, was validated by the three WP6 partner organisations, given their potential interest of interoperability solutions and their experience in integrating different identifier systems as part of their services.

Deviations from DoW/ impact on other tasks

None have been observed.

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	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final

Use of resources (including actual vs. planned)

Table 4. WP4 person-months per partner compared with the DoW.

No.	Short name	PM expected to be spent during the first 12 months of the project	PM spent in WP4
1	ANDS	0.0	0.0
2	arXiv	0.0	0.0
3	BL	1.5	0.0
4	CERN	0.5	0.0
5	DataCite	6.0	6.7
6	DRYAD	0.0	0.0
7	ORCID	4.5	5.5
TOTAL		12.5	12.1

BL will have a more active role in the development of WP4 during the second year of the project. BL (3 p/m) and CERN's (1p/m) (main input into this work package will after MS5 'Commonalities Identified' (Month 17) which provides WP3 input into the WP4 proof of concept (task 4.5) in the 2nd year.

2.2.4. WP5 – Strategy

Summary of progress towards objectives and details for each task/significant results

The main objective of this work package is to enable the implementation of the ‘missing thin layer’ of interoperable, open, persistent identifiers in the architecture of the Collaborative Data Infrastructure proposed by HLEG in 2010¹⁸.

The WP5 work is focused on identifying the gaps that hinder implementation of the ‘thin layer’. The approach builds on a detailed assessment of the current gaps and practices. Special emphasis is given to the experience and ideas of the individual stakeholder groups, e-infrastructure providers, research communities, publishers, policy makers. This is combined with a draft roadmap that includes recommendations to address and close such gaps. This overall consensus building approach shall enable future actions to be supported by all relevant communities.

In practice, during the first 12 months of the project the main objective of WP5 has been to develop a gap analysis and a draft roadmap, to build a network of expertise and connections to relevant stakeholders. This has been published together with a stakeholder specific SWOT analysis. The output from the kick-off event framed a good starting point, and the participation in the ORCID Outreach Meeting, Symposium on Research Attribution, and the ORCID Codefest, in May 2013 in Oxford UK constituted a

¹⁸ <http://cordis.europa.eu/fp7/ict/e-infrastructure/docs/hlg-sdi-report.pdf>

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major step in the development of this work package. They had an impact on all activities in this WP, beyond the 1st year. During the first year a close collaboration with other work packages has been accomplished.

Activities by task

Task 5.1 – Prepare for Kick-Off, M1 – M2 (CERN, all)

The Kick-Off event has been prepared in strong collaboration with WP2. A comprehensive set of speakers has been selected to represent all the relevant stakeholders (e-infrastructure providers, libraries, publishers, 3rd party services using PIDs). The topics of discussion were carefully planned with these experts in advance to the meeting, i.e. focussing on the challenges on a disciplinary layer (e.g. with 2 speakers from the HSS) or on the interoperability of two global services (ORCID-SCOPUS integration). Speakers with interesting use-cases for persistent identification in scholarly communication contributed to the discussion.

Task 5.2 – Gap analysis and draft roadmap, M2 – M11 (CERN, BL)

The presentations and the discussion from the kick-off event have been used as a first input for the gap analysis. In addition, relevant developments and publications have been incorporated. Interviews with the main stakeholders in the field of PIDs for author and objects have been conducted in spring 2013 to provide in depth insights into the main challenges. A multi-stakeholder approach had been chosen. The results highlight the risk of silo solutions in the current e-infrastructure environment and an urgent need for action. A need for strong collaboration among stakeholders to address the most prominent gaps is evident. In order to build a base for cross-disciplinary value added services, it is needed to build an open, interoperable and participative PID infrastructure. These need to connect an open sharing environment and the academic reward and incentive mechanisms.

During the first year of WP5, special emphasis has been given to liaising with external experts, beyond the ODIN project e.g. from other disciplines or infrastructure providers. This has happened throughout the 1st year, as well as during the final months of the 1st year (see Task 5.3 below). This approach is considered a crucial step for ODIN, in order to validate the statements within the gap analysis and draft roadmap. It is intended to build on the successful experience in the 2nd year.

Task 5.3 Validation and feedback M11 – 12 (CERN, All)

The draft roadmap has been validated through three concurrent steps, first through the engagement of external experts with the interviews. Then, it has been presented during the ODIN first year event at CERN (Oct 17th, 2013). There, it has been exposed to a group of international leaders and stakeholders in the field of PIDs.

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In addition, the draft roadmap has been reviewed by an external group of experts, the authors of the DIGODUNA report, this report can be found in Annex 1.

The review of the gap analysis and draft roadmap by the international partners of the project is presented in D6.1.

Deviations from DoW/ impact on other tasks

With agreement from the Project Officer D5.1 was submitted late, due to challenge of carrying out external reviews over the summer months, which in turn originated from the original starting date of the project, this had the knock on effect of delaying Task 6.3 Review of material M11-M12, which needed to review the completed D5.1

Use of resources (including actual vs. planned)

Table 5 WP5 person-months per partner compared with the DoW.

No.	Short name	PM expected to be spent during the first 12 months of the project	PM spent in WP5
1	ANDS	0.0	0.0
2	arXiv	0.0	0.0
3	BL	1.0	0.0
4	CERN	5.5	7.4
5	DataCite	0.5	0.0
6	DRYAD	0.0	0.0
7	ORCID	0.5	0.0
TOTAL		7.5	7.4

Minor deviations in use of resources for this WP are an artefact of a linear interpolation of effort over the first year. DataCite effort in WP5 (1 PM) will be mainly focus on the development of the final roadmap (DoW task 5.5), following the incorporation of the validated proofs and interoperability after month 18, (DoW task 5.4), which is the main focus of BL's effort in this work package (2PM).

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
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2.2.5. WP6 – Internationalisation

Summary of progress towards objectives and details for each task/significant results

To be successful globally, the solutions proposed by ODIN must address the concerns of those global audiences. WP6 provides an additional mechanism for validating that relevance.

Activities by task

Task 6.1 Preparation for kick off and communication, M1- M2 (ANDS, all)

The Internationalisation work package (WP6) received valuable input at the kick-off meeting from a broader range of international stakeholders beyond those that are formally partners the ODIN project. Global information services such as Elsevier¹⁹ and VIAF²⁰/ISNI provided significant perspectives on the scientific challenges of international researcher identification. Differing cultural perspectives were evident in inputs from the USA (SSRN Publishing) and Japan (The National Institute for Informatics) with important commonalities noted in the approaches to tracking datasets across national boundaries.

The second, internal day of the kick-off meeting established reliable intra-project processes for incorporating kick-off inputs and future feedback into the project deliverables (particularly at the critical project junctures of month 12 and 18). Timetables and responsibilities were confirmed for ANDS, arXiv and Dryad to both have input into and review project deliverables with processes for validating proposals from international perspectives.

Task 6.2 Agile validation in the first year, M2-M11 (ANDS, all)

WP6 partners have been in regular contact with the rest of the consortium via electronic communications and fortnightly project team conference calls. In addition, the following visits by WP6 participants to European partners provided input into work: Simeon Warner from arXiv visited CERN in March (M7), Steve McEachern from The Australian Data Archive visited BL in May (M8), Dryad software developer (Ryan Scherle) met with ORCID and DataCite staff in the UK for one week in April (M8) and Todd Vision visited DataCite, ORCID and CERN over M8 and M9.

Following the collaboration with ODIN partners on the interoperability model, ANDS has integrated DataCite and ORCID identifiers, and adopted the provided model by ODIN D 5.1. This interoperability model enhanced ANDS services by enabling Australian

¹⁹ <http://www.elsevier.com/>

²⁰ <http://viaf.org/>

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researchers and their international collaborators to import their research datasets into their ORCID profiles.

Task 6.3 Review of material M11-M12 (ANDS, all)

The output from the first phase of the project has undergone a thorough peer review process by the ANDS, DRYAD and arXiv (non-EU partners of the project) between months 11 and 12. They have reviewed the ODIN proof of concepts of WP3 and WP4, the gap analysis and draft roadmap (D3.1, D3.2 and D5.1). This synoptic validation by external partners offered an additional international and independent viewpoint, taking into account the range of discussions covered in the first year event. Finally, a written report on the review process has been published in which the broad applicability of the first year results is assessed.

In addition, ANDS, DRYAD and arXiv have actively participated at the 1st year event/Codesprint.

Deviations from DoW/ impact on other tasks

With agreement from the Project Officer D6.1 was submitted late, due to the knock on effect given for extra time allowed for D5.1

Use of resources (including actual vs. planned)

Table 6 WP6 person-months per partner compared with the DoW.

No.	Short name	PM expected to be spent during the first 12 months of the project	PM spent in WP6
1	ANDS	2.0	3.9
2	arXiv	1.0	0.8
3	BL	0.0	0.0
4	CERN	0.0	0.0
5	DataCite	0.0	0.0
6	DRYAD	1.0	1.2
7	ORCID	0.0	0.0
TOTAL		4.0	5.6

Additional effort has been recorded by ANDS. This additional effort is mainly result of extra activities by ANDS for ORCID integration. This integration is now live and researchers can import datasets from Research Data Australia on the ORCID website. All ODIN activities from extra-European partners are self-funded.

	D1.3 First year report		
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2.3. Project management during the period

The main tasks of WP1 (Project Coordination) and their achievements are summarized below.

Task 1.1: Administrative and Financial co-ordination, M1 - M24 (BL)

The Project Coordinator outlined the obligation and responsibilities of each partner to keep records of expenditure and resources used in the project at the 1st project meeting in October 2012. The Coordinator provides reminders to all partners to maintain timesheets and to fill effort report on a regular basis in the internal wiki. The project coordinator also monitors the progress of tasks and keeps the risk register updated on the wiki. The pre-financing was received from the Commission and distributed according to the Consortium Agreement.

Task 1.2: Project Quality Plan, M1 (BL)

The Project Quality Plan includes provisions such as internal reporting procedures, configuration management arrangements, standard project document templates and use of management tools. The Plan was produced and submitted as deliverable D1.1 Project Quality Plan and Risk Register. The Risk Register has also been regularly updated on the project wiki.

Task 1.3: Define impact metrics, M1 (BL)

A project plan with deadlines for project milestones and deliverables and dependencies was developed in M1 and fed into the Project Quality Plan. This project plan is available on the project intranet and constantly monitored.

Task 1.4: Risk register, M1 – M24 (BL, DATACITE, CERN, ANDS)

The risk register was put in place and available on the project wiki and it is constantly updated and monitored. All partners have access to it and have the possibility to edit and add risks. An initial risk register was submitted as part of D1.1.

Task 1.5: Consortium management, M1 – M24 (BL, DataCite)

The project consortium agreement has been signed by all project partners. Records of consortium management are kept on the project wiki. There is regular communication between the Consortium Members via email and fortnightly telephone calls. Face to face meetings between the European partners are held at a minimum frequency of 6 months. Effort is recorded for each partner and work package on a monthly basis through the project wiki. Templates have been created for deliverables and reports to ensure compliance with the project quality plan.

Deviations from DoW/ impact on other tasks

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	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
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D1.1 was submitted late mainly due to BL hiring additional project staff that started in Feb 2013. This caused no other impact on any other work.

Use of resources (including actual vs. planned)

Table 7: WP1 person-months per partner compared with the DoW.

No.	Short name	PM expected to be spent during the first 12 months of the project	PM spent in WP1
1	ANDS	0.0	0.0
2	arXiv	0.0	0.0
3	BL	5.0	3.1
4	CERN	0.5	0.2
5	DataCite	1.5	3.0
6	DRYAD	0.0	0.0
7	ORCID	0.5	0.0
TOTAL		7.5	6.2

BL has recorded less project management effort than planned in the first year. This is mainly to do with expending more effort on the disciplinary proof of concept in WP3. DataCite invested more effort than initially planned due to the preparation of the deliverable D1.2 First interim scientific report and the support provided to the Project Coordinator during the first year.

Project Meetings

Telephone meetings have been held on a fortnightly basis throughout the first year. Due to challenges faced by the global nature of the partners these alternate between Morning in Europe to facilitate Australian participation and Afternoon in Europe to facilitate US partners participation.

A number of face to face meetings have also been held within the first year to monitor the status of the project, review plans for completing tasks, milestones and deliverables and to plan for future work.

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Table 8: face to face meetings.

Date	Venue	Purpose
19/10/2012	Berlin	First project planning meeting
04/05/02/2013	London (British Library)	Scientific deliverables progress and planning meeting (European partners)
25/06/2013	Geneva (CERN)	Scientific deliverables progress and planning meeting (European partners)
18/10/2013	Geneva (CERN)	Overview of 1 st year and 2 nd year planning meeting and General Assembly

Project planning and status

The status of the project is fully satisfactory. All scientific deliverables for the first year were submitted by M13 and all contracted deliverables for the first year will be submitted by M14. Actions for tasks, activities and deliverables for all work packages have been planned for the second year.

Impact of possible deviations for the planned milestones and deliverables

The DoW schedules the second year event for M23, July 2014, however as per year one it may be prudent to re-schedule the event to M25 or M26. This is due to often low attendance at events in the European summer time. This would have the effect of delaying the publication of D2.4, Final communication report including results from final event (currently M24) until after the event has been held. The project co-ordinator will discuss this with EC.

Development of the Project Website

The project website is operational at <http://odin-project.eu/>

2.4. Deliverables and milestones tables

2.4.1. Table of Deliverables

TABLE 1. DELIVERABLES										
Del. no.	Deliverable name	Version	WP no.	Lead beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination level ²¹	Delivery date from Annex I (proj month)	Actual / Forecast delivery date Dd/mm/yyyy	Status No submitted/ Submitted	Comments
D1.1	Project Quality Plan & Project Risk Register	3.0	1	BL	Report	Public	09/12	01/13	Submitted	Late submission due to BL hiring project staff
D2.1	Kick-off preparation, Communication plan and Website	4.0	2	ORCID	Report	Public	09/12	12/12	Submitted	Late submission due to ORCID hiring project staff

PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services).

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services).

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

Make sure that you are using the correct following label when your project has classified deliverables.

EU restricted = Classified with the mention of the classification level restricted "EU Restricted"

EU confidential = Classified with the mention of the classification level confidential " EU Confidential "

EU secret = Classified with the mention of the classification level secret "EU Secret "

	D1.3 First year report			
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT			Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final	35/56

D2.2	Kick-off report	7.0	2	ORCID	Report	Public	09/12	01/13	Submitted	Late submission due to ORCID hiring project staff
D1.2	First interim scientific report	2.0	1	DataCite	Report	Public	02/13	03/13	Submitted	Late submission agreed with PO to collate 6 moths effort
D3.1	Proof of concept HSS	1.1	3	British Library	Report	Public	07/13	08/13	Submitted	
D3.2	Proof of concept HEP	1.0	3	CERN	Report	Public	07/13	07/13	Submitted	
D4.1	Conceptual model of interoperability	1.0	4	DataCite	Report	Public	07/13	08/13	Submitted	
D5.1	Gap analysis and draft roadmap	1.0	5	CERN	Report	Public	07/13	09/13	Submitted	Late submission agreed with PO to accommodate external input
D6.1	International review of final outputs	1.4	6	ANDS	Report	Public	08/13	09/13	Submitted	Late submission agreed with PO in order to review D5.1

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
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D2.3	First year communication report including results from first year event	1.0	2	ORCID	Report	Public	08/13	10/13	Submitted	Late submission agreed with PO as event was re-scheduled
D1.3	First year report	1.0	1	BL	Report	Public	10/13	10/13	Submitted	

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 37/56

2.4.2. Table of Milestones

TABLE 2. MILESTONES							
Milestone no.	Milestone name	Work package no	Lead beneficiary	Delivery date from Annex I dd/mm/yyyy	Achieved Yes/No	Actual / Forecast achievement date dd/mm/yyyy	Comments
MS1	Agreements concluded	WP1	BL	30/09/2012	Yes	09/04/13	All partners acceded to the consortium agreement.
MS2	Kick-off complete	WP2	ORCID EU	30/11/2012	Yes	16/01/2012	D2.2 Kick-off report submitted
MS3	Mid-term conference	WP2	ORCID EU	01/07/2013	Yes	17/10/2013	Conference held in Geneva.
MS7	Gap Analysis Completed	WP5	CERN	Verification:	Yes	20/05/2013	Drafting of roadmap starts

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT	Dissemination level: PU	
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)	Version: 2_0 Final	38/56

2.5. Explanation of the use of the resources and financial statements

The financial statements have to be provided within the Forms C for each beneficiary (if Special Clause 10 applies to your Grant Agreement, a separate financial statement is provided for each third party as well) together with a summary financial report which consolidates the claimed Community contribution of all the beneficiaries in an aggregate form, based on the information provided in Form C (Annex VI of the Grant Agreement) by each beneficiary.

The "Explanation of use of resources" requested in the Grant Agreement for personnel costs, subcontracting, any major costs (ex: purchase of important equipment, travel costs, large consumable items) and indirect costs, have now to be done within the Forms (user guides are accessible within the Participant Portal)²².

When applicable, certificates on financial statements shall be submitted by the concerned beneficiaries according to Article II.4.4 of the Grant Agreement.

Besides the electronic submission, Forms C as well as certificates (if applicable), have to be signed and sent in parallel by post.

²² In the past, the explanation of use of resources requested in the Grant Agreement was done within a table in this section. The merge of this table within the Forms C was a measure of simplification aimed at avoiding duplication and/or potential discrepancies between the data provided in the table 'Explanation of use of resources' and the data provided in the Forms C.

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	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 39/56

2.5.1. Explanation of Use of Resources by Organisation

Table 9 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 1 for the period. THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD					
Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP1	Personnel costs	15,006 €	Total funded effort 3.07 p/m	Head of Department 0.55 p/m and Senior Staff 2.52 p/m	Head of Department is Jude England (0.55p/m), Senior Staff is John Kaye (2.37 p/m) and Tom Demeranville (0.15 p/m)
WP1	Other direct cost	1,864 €	Travel and Other Direct Costs: Travel 1441€, Other 362€	1 person attended ODIN Kick off meeting 18.10.12 Berlin, Germany - EC FP7 Project Coordinators day 23.10.2012 Brussels, Belgium - ODIN Project Meeting 4-5.02.2013, London, UK - ODIN project meeting, 25.06.2013, Geneva, Switzerland - Other direct costs include room and catering for the BL ODIN Project meeting and document courier costs	John Kaye attended all these events for WP1 duties
WP2	Personnel costs	1,909 €	0.39 p/m funded	Head of department: 0.05 p/m, Senior Staff: 0.34 p/m	Head of Department is Jude England (0.05 p/m), Senior Staff are John Kaye (0.29 p/m) and Tom Demeranville (0.5 p/m)
WP3	Personnel costs	41,835 €	11.72 p/m reported effort. 8.55 p/m funded and 3.17 p/m unfunded	Head of Department 0.34 p/m unfunded. Senior staff 8.55 p/m funded and 2.84 p/m unfunded	Head of Department is Jude England (0.34 p/m), Senior Staff are John Kaye (5.03 p/m) and Tom Demeranville (5.9 p/m - 2.84 p/m unfunded)

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 40/56

Table 9 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 1 for the period. THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP2	Other direct cost	2,065 €	Travel expenses for ODIN Kick Off and ORCID Launch for JISC names	Amanda Hill from the JISC names project/Mimas attended ODIN Kick off meeting 18.10.12 Belin, Germany. Amanda travelled from Canada.	
WP3	Other direct cost	4,615 €	Travel Expenses for Steve McEachern- Australian Data Archive. Visit to BL on behalf of ANDS	Steve McEachern visited BL 11.05.13 - 02.06.13 to work on HSS proof of concept. Expenses include flights from Sydney Australia, accommodation in London, travel to UK Data Archive, Colchester, Essex on 20.05.13 - Travel and accommodation at ORCID outreach meeting, Oxford 21-24.06.13	

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 41/56

Table 9 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 1 for the period. THE BRITISH LIBRARY BOARD

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP3			Travel and Other Direct Costs: Travel 4142€, Other 1106€	1 person attended ODIN Kick off meeting 18.10.12 Belin, Germany- - meeting with UK Data Service, 20.01.13, Colchester Essex - IASSIST Conference 27-31.05.2013, Cologne, Germany. 2 staff attended BL internal project meeting, Cheltenham, UK, 21.01.2013 prior to new ODIN staff commencing work - ODIN Project Meeting 4-5.02.2013, London, UK - ORCID Outreach Meeting, 21-24.05.2013, Oxford, UK - ODIN project meeting, 25.06.2013, Geneva, Switzerland. Travel Expenses were also paid for Brigitte Hausstein (GESIS) to travel from Berlin to Cologne for ODIN IASSIST session. Other direct costs include IASSIST conference feesfor BL, ORCID and DataCite as well as - Membership of IASSIST and ISNI- Domain nameand web hosting for odin-discover.eu	Jude England attended ODIN Kick Off meeting. John Kaye attended UKDS Meeting. John Kaye and Tom Demeranville Attended Cheltenham meeting, ORCID outreach meeting and ODIN Geneva meeting
	Indirect costs	43,525 €			

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 42/56

Table 10 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 2 for the period. MONASH UNIVERSITY

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP6	Personnel costs	2,653 €	Scientific Specialist costs	Site visit to BL and specialist HSS input into 3.1 and 6.1	Steve McEachern from Australian Data Archive (0.5 p/m)
WP6	Personnel costs	15,675 €	Scientific Staff costs	Regular telephone meetings, review and input into D3.1, D3.2, D4.1, and D5.1, planning, development, and coordination of D6.1, validation of 4.1 within ANDS systems, input and planning for end of first year event	Amir Aryani (2.48 p/m)
WP6	Personnel costs	5,787 €	Senior Staff costs	Participation in kick off meeting in Berlin in October 2012, regular telephone meetings, review and input into D3.1 and D5.1, planning, development, and coordination of D6.1, oversight of validation of 4.1 within ANDS systems	Adrian Burton (0.92 p/m)
	Indirect costs	0 €			
TOTAL COSTS		24,115 €			

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 43/56

Table 11 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 3 for the period. CORNELL UNIVERSITY CORPORATION

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP6	Personnel costs	6,739 €	Senior staff costs 0.85 p/m	Participation in kick off meeting in Berlin in October 2012, visited CERN March 2013, participated in Oxford Hackathon April 2013, regular telephone meetings, reviewed deliverables and provided input into D4.1. Total 0.85 p/m.	Simeon Warner (0.85 p/m)
	Indirect costs	4,043 €			
TOTAL COSTS		10,782 €			

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 44/56

Table 12 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 4 for the period. DATACITE – INTERNATIONAL DATA CITATION INITIATIVE

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP1	Personnel costs	8,995 €	Total effort reported: 10.2 PM. Total effort claimed: 6.7 PM. 2.8 PM charged to Management.	Jan Brase (senior staff) and Sergio Ruiz (senior staff).	Jan Brase (1.4 p/m) Sergio Ruiz (1.4 p/m)
WP1	Other direct cost	100 €	Travel costs Jan Brase (senior staff) for WP1.	Jan Brase (senior staff) participated in kick-off meeting in Berlin (Germany), October 19 2012.	
WP2, WP3, WP4	Personnel costs	28,336 €	Total effort reported: 10.2 PM. Total effort claimed: 6.7 PM. 7.4 PM charged to WP2, WP3 and WP4.	Jan Brase (senior staff): 5.5 PM invested in the project. Only 1.9 PM charged to ODIN. His salary before April 2012 has been paid by a different organization, therefore is not claimed. Sergio Ruiz (senior staff): 4.8 PM.	WP2: Jan Brase (0.4 p/m), Sergio Ruiz (0.1 p/m) - WP3: Jan Brase (0.2 p/m) - WP2: Jan Brase (3.5 p/m), Sergio Ruiz (3.15 p/m)

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 45/56

Table 12 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 4 for the period. DATACITE – INTERNATIONAL DATA CITATION INITIATIVE

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP4	Other direct cost	4,376 €	Travel costs Sergio Ruiz (senior staff) for WP4.	Sergio Ruiz (senior staff) participated in deliverables meeting in London (UK), February 4 and 5 2013. He worked with John Kaye (Project Coordinator) in WP4 preparation, February 6 and 7 2013. Sergio Ruiz (senior staff) participated in a meeting with EPIC in Hannover (Germany), February 12. He participated in a WP4 meeting in Hannover (Germany), February 13. Meeting with Jan Brase (senior staff) in Hannover (Germany), February 14 2013. Sergio Ruiz (senior staff) participated in a WP4 meeting in Hannover (Germany), April 3 and 4 2013. Sergio Ruiz gave an ODIN Talk at the CRECS Conference in Seville (Spain), May 09 2013. Sergio Ruiz attended the The Now and Future of Data Publishing workshop and the ORCID Outreach Meeting in Oxford (UK), May 22 and 23 2013. Sergio Ruiz gave an ODIN Talk at the FESABID Conference in Toledo (Spain), May 25 2013. Sergio Ruiz participated in an ODIN Meeting in Geneva (Switzerland), June 25 2013.	
	Indirect costs	8,361 €			
TOTAL COSTS		50,168 €			

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 46/56

Table 13 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 5 for the period. EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP1	Other direct cost	4,611 €	Travel costs (4394.39€) and Other costs (216.45€)	1 Person attended ODIN KO Meeting 18.10.2012, Berlin, Germany - ODIN Project Meeting 4-5.02.2013, London, UK - EU Concertation meeting 07.02.2013, Brussels, Belgium - 10th e-Infrastructure Concertation Meeting, 06.07.03.2013, Brussels, Belgium - Research Data Alliance Conference, 17-20.03.2013, Gothenburg, Sweden - EIROForum meeting, 22.03.2013, Brussels, Belgium- ODIN project meeting, 25.06.2013, Geneva, Switzerland (Other Direct Costs)	Travel for Salvatore Mele (Senior staff) and Other Direct Costs
WP1	Personnel costs	0 €	0.26PM Unfunded (0.04PM Fellow + 0.22PM Senior Staff)		Fellow: Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen (0.04 p/m) - Senior Staff: Salvatore Mele (0.22 p/m)
WP2	Other direct cost	2,209 €	Travel costs	1 person attended ORCID/DataCite WS 21.05.2013, London, UK - 2 Persons attended ORCID Outreach Meeting, 21-24.05.2013, Oxford, UK	ORCID/DataCite WS : Fellow Laura Rueda ORCID Outreach Meeting : Fellow Laura Rueda + Senior Staff Salvatore Mele
WP3	Other direct cost	2,634 €	Travel costs (1414€) and Other costs (1220€)	1 person attended ODIN KO Meeting 18.10.2012, Berlin, Germany - ODIN Project Meeting 4-5.02.2013, London, UK - 1 Invited Guest Scientist invited to WP3 meeting at CERN 10-15.03.2013, Geneva, Switzerland	Travel for the Fellow Laura Rueda and Guest Scientists visiting from arXiv (Simeon Warner)

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 47/56

Table 13 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 5 for the period. EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP5	Other direct cost	2,097 €	Travel costs	1 person attended: ODIN KO Meeting 18.10.2012, Berlin, Germany - ODIN Project Meeting 4-5.02.2013, London, UK- ORCID /DataCite WS 21.05.2013, London, UK - ORCID Outreach Meeting 21-24.05.2013, Oxford, UK	Travel for Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen (Fellow)
WP2	Personnel costs	15,696 €	5.33PM (5.09PM Funded + 0.24PM Unfunded)	Funded : 4.85PM Admin Student + 0.24PM Fellow / Unfunded : 0.20PM Fellow + 0.04PM Senior Staff	Admin Student: Neli Ivanova (4.85PM) Fellow: Laura Rueda (0.24PM) Unfunded Fellow : Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen (0.20PM) and unfunded Senior Staff: Salvatore Mele (0.04PM)
WP3	Personnel costs	82,569 €	20.84PM (20.43PM Funded + 0.41PM Unfunded)	Funded : 14PM Technical Student + 6.43PM Fellow / Unfunded : 0.09PM Fellow + 0.32PM Senior Staff	Technical Students: Thomas Karampelas (12PM) + Soe Minn Htoo (2PM) Fellow: Laura Rueda (6.43PM) Unfunded Fellow : Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen (0.09PM) and unfunded Senior Staff: Salvatore Mele (0.32PM)
WP5	Personnel costs	26,980 €	7.46PM (4.79PM Funded + 2.67PM Unfunded)	Funded : 1.15PM Admin Student + 3.64PM Fellow / Unfunded : 0.46PM Doctoral Student + 2.18PM Fellow + 0.03PM Senior Staff	Admin Student: Neli Ivanova (1.15PM) Fellow: Laura Rueda (3.64PM) Unfunded : Fellow Suenje Dallmeier-Tiessen (2.18PM) + Doctoral Student Patricia Herterich (0.46PM) and Senior Staff Salvatore Mele (0.03PM)
	Indirect costs	27,359 €			

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 48/56

Table 13 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 5 for the period. EUROPEAN ORGANIZATION FOR NUCLEAR RESEARCH

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
TOTAL COSTS		164,155 €			

Table 14 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 6 for the period. DUKE UNIVERSITY

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP6	Personnel costs	8,114 €	Senior Scientist (0.97 p/m) Scientist (0.22 p/m)	Participation in kick off meeting in Berlin in October 2012, Scientist and Senior Scientist visited DataCite and ORCID in May 2013, participated in Oxford Hackathon May 2013, regular telephone meetings, reviewed deliverables and provided input into D6.1.	Senior Scientist: Todd Vision (0.97 p/m), Scientist Ryan Scherle (0.22 p/m)
	Indirect costs	1,622 €			
TOTAL COSTS		9,736 €			

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 49/56

Table 15 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 7 for the period. ORCID EU

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
WP2	Personnel costs	27,062 €	7.2 PM (0.8 PM Unfunded + 6.4 PM Funded)	Funded: 1.4 PM Outreach Fellow, 5.0 PM Technical Fellow / Unfunded: 0.8M Senior Staff	Outreach Fellow: Martin Fenner (1.4 p/m) - Technical Fellow: Gudmundur Thorisson (5.0 p/m) - Senior Staff: Laure Haak (0.8p/m unfunded)
WP4	Personnel costs	24,512 €	5.5 PM (0.2PM Unfunded + 5.3 PM Funded)	Funded: 2.1 PM Outreach Fellow + 3.2 PM Technical Fellow / Unfunded 0.2 PM Senior Staff	Outreach Fellow: Martin Fenner (1.4 p/m) - Technical Fellow: Gudmundur Thorisson (5.0 p/m) - Senior Staff: Laure Haak (0.8p/m unfunded)
WP2	Other direct cost	8,938 €	Travel Costs	2 people attended ODIN/ORCID CodeFest 24.05.2013, 1 person attended ODIN Project meeting (2013.02.05, London); 1 person attended EU briefing on digital identifiers (2013.02.07, London); 1 person attended EGU meeting (2013.04.10, Vienna); 2 ORCID EU people and 2 Dryad people attended ODIN Meeting (2013.04.03, Hannover); 1 person attended Knowledge Exchange wrkshop (2013.04.12, Berlin); 2 people attended ORCID/ODIN codefest (2013.05.24, Oxford); 1 person attended IGSN/ DataCite/Pangaea/ ORCID EU CodeSpring (2013.07.01, Potsdam)	M. Fenner and G. Thorisson attended ODIN/ORCID CodeFest - M. Fenner attended ODIN Project meeting - M. Fenner attended EU briefing on digital identifiers - M. Fenner attended EGU meeting - M. Fenner and G. Thorisson (ORCID) and Todd Vision and Ryan Scherle (Dryad) attended ODIN Meeting. M. Fenner attended Knowledge Exchange workshop. M. Fenner attended GSN/ DataCite/Pangaea/ ORCID EU CodeSpring
WP2	Other direct cost	5,898 €	Event Organizing	Facilities, Speaker Travel, and Catering for ODIN KO meeting (2012.10.18)	€5,898 covers venue, catering and speaker dinner. Speaker travel of €1,239 (Simeon Warner) was not included in this total and will be claimed in the next period. Staff Travel to the event of €908 for M Fenner and G Thorisson was not included in this total and will be claimed in the next period

	D1.3 First year report		
	WP1: PROJECT MANAGEMENT		Dissemination level: PU
	Authors: Sergio Ruiz (DataCite), John Kaye (British Library)		Version: 2_0 Final 50/56

Table 15 Personnel, subcontracting and other Major cost items for beneficiary 7 for the period. ORCID EU

Work Package	Item description	Amount in €	Explanation	Free Text	Additional Explanation
	Indirect costs	2,247 €			
TOTAL COSTS		68,657 €			

3. ANNEX 1: EVALUATION OF ODIN FROM THE DIGOIDUNA STUDY²³

The general objective of the DIGOIDUNA study was to provide an analysis of the role and impact of persistent identifiers for digital objects and authors within the context of scientific data e-infrastructures (SDIs) and propose a set of requirements and recommendations, which policy makers should address to fill the current gaps and bootstrap an identifier eco-system delivering new value to SDIs.

The results from the DIGOIDUNA study represent an important starting point and a valuable input for the ODIN project since both studies have several commonalities in focus, objectives and methodology.

This section summarizes the key aspects of the evaluation of the ODIN project from the DIGOIDUNA perspective. The aim of this evaluation is to highlight how the ODIN project is following the DIGOIDUNA approach and recommendations and which findings from DIGOIDUNA can still feed into ODIN to orient and enhance future work.

3.1. Commonalities in Objectives, Methodology and General Approach

We have identified several commonalities between the two studies in terms of objectives, methodology and general approach.

- First of all, both studies focuses on the role of **persistent identifiers (PIDs) for digital objects and authors** as enablers of value for e-science infrastructures and aim to **show the benefits** of a systematic usage of PIDs for access, attribution and trust of scientific data.
- To this purpose DIGOIDUNA presents some **scenarios** as examples of the beneficial impact of PIDs in e-science, while ODIN analyses several **uses cases** of interoperability between PID solutions for authors and data.
- The **SWOT analysis** is adopted by both studies to analyse the current situation, identify the future objectives and opportunities and highlight the gaps that need to be filled. Based on the results of the SWOT analysis (and GAP analysis in ODIN), both studies propose a set of **actions and recommendations** to fill the identified gaps and develop an open and sustainable e-infrastructure for digital objects and author PIDs.
- The **stakeholder participation and validation** of the results is another common aspect between DIGOIDUNA and ODIN. In the DIGOIDUNA study, the coordination and agreement between the key stakeholder communities is identified as one of the most critical action to address the fragmentation of the PID ecosystem and enable the creation of a sustainable and coordinated PID infrastructure. On the same way, ODIN put the same attention for the representation of all the relevant stakeholder groups in all the project activities in order to encourage collaboration, address specific issues, identify new services and tools, propose use cases and solutions, and finally to build the level of

²³ DIGOIDUNA. Digital Object Identifiers and Unique Authors Identifiers to Enable Services for Data Quality Assessment, Provenance and Access. Report for Experts Feedback. Università degli Studi di Trento: 2011. Available at: http://namesproject.files.wordpress.com/2011/12/digoiduna_final_report_expert_feedback.pdf

	D1.3 First year report		
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- consensus which is needed to implement the interoperability layer and overcome the identified challenges.
- Another aspect that ODIN shares with DIGOIDUNA is the **multidimensional and cross-boundary perspective** to diagnose the current situation and propose integrated actions. Following this approach, for example, ODIN adopts a cross-disciplinary view in conducting two proofs of concept in two very different domains (HSS and HEP). An international perspective is also adopted to make the proposed solution globally successful.
 - The **attention for the Linked Open Data approach** and the development of an interoperable identification solution exploiting the potential of the Web of Data is a further commonality between the two studies and it is also fully in line with the Den Haag manifesto²⁴.
 - Another aspect concerning the general approach is that both studies adhere to the so-called “**Don’t reinvent the wheel principle**”. According to this principle, to bootstrap an interoperable identifier ecosystem it is necessary to consolidate established PID systems, and engage them to deliver concrete value within SDIs by making these systems interoperable, instead of proposing a new identification solution ex novo or promoting the proliferation of a multiplicity of ad hoc solutions. Following this principle, ODIN is working to build on the success of DataCite and ORCID by designing an interoperability layer for persistent author and object identifiers.
 - In both studies **technology is not the first concern**. ODIN follows the DIGOIDUNA recommendation that the first step toward the development of an interoperable PID ecosystem for digital objects and authors is **to build on common understanding and agreeing on common objectives** before addressing technological issues. This means that building the interoperability layer between PIDs for authors and digital objects is far to be a technological problem, dealing with organizational, political, economical, legal and other social aspects.
 - ODIN shares the DIGOIDUNA view that the definition of **added-value services** on top of the interoperability infrastructure is a fundamental early step in the design of the infrastructure and it is crucial to incentivize its adoption. Stakeholders should participate in the definition of these services, like in all the other phases of the design and development.

3.2. Building on the DIGOIDUNA recommendations

The DIGOIDUNA study proposes four sets of recommendations. We used them as a framework to evaluate if the ODIN project is generally in line with the DIGOIDUNA

²⁴ <http://www.knowledge-exchange.info/Default.aspx?ID=462>

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results and how some specific recommendations can be exploited to enhance the ODIN future work.

Define the PDIs agenda:

- 1. Defining the common objectives and organize them into a list of workable temporal priorities.**
- 2. Agreeing on a shared governance model, which defines devolved responsibilities amongst stakeholders and ensures long-term sustainability.**
- 3. Sharing a conceptual framework in which the basic technical parameters and the fundamental services are introduced and described.**
- 4. Planning interventions to promote awareness, dissemination and education activities aiming at expanding and reinforcing DI knowledge and skills.**

In line with the first set of recommendations:

- ODIN follows the DIGOIDUNA recommendation of working on the definition of a common conceptual framework (i.e. a common agenda among key stakeholders) and agreeing on a common roadmap of objectives and added-value services before addressing technical issues.
- ODIN is also in line with the DIGOIDUNA view of involving different stakeholder communities in the definition of objectives, in defining a common roadmap and in the design, implementation and adoption of the PID interoperability layer.
- ODIN recognizes the importance of dissemination activities to promote general consensus and build shared understanding and internationalization.
- ODIN aims to address the specific needs of individual stakeholders but also adopts a cross boundary focus on common aspects and requirements among the user communities.

Building on the DIGOIDUNA recommendations:

- It is important that the ODIN roadmap organizes common objectives into a list of workable temporal priorities.
- Key stakeholders should be involved in the definition of a shared governance model defining responsibilities among stakeholders to ensure long-term sustainability of the interoperability layer.

Bootstrapping DIs in SDIs

- 1. Reinforce, promote and secure EU wide institutional coordination among vertical and regional clusters of e-infrastructure stakeholders (common policies on the governance of identifiers for digital objects and authors).**
- 2. Funding bodies must provide initial support to seed initiatives, which aim at implementing the coordination model defined in the agenda and at creating a critical mass of coordinated DI systems.**

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3. **Promote awareness and skills development to enable different stakeholders to participate effectively on DI initiatives and infrastructures.**
4. **Work towards systematic implementation of technical and organisational factors that underpin trust in identifiers, their reliability as a key component of SDIs - secure their operational management.**

In line with the second set of recommendations:

- ODIN follows the DIGOIDUNA indication of raising awareness among stakeholders by providing concrete evidence of the valuable impact of the proposed solution. To this purpose, two proofs of concepts in two different domains are proposed. Moreover ODIN aims to involve scientific communities with no experience in PIDs for data and contributors.
- ODIN aims to promote coordination and interoperability between local and community specific solutions.
- ODIN agrees with DIGOIDUNA that funding bodies should provide initial economical support to seed the emerging PID infrastructure.
- Enabling third-party services and producing other tangible outputs (e.g. proofs of concept) is seen by ODIN like DIGOIDUNA a fundamental step to provide evidence of the reliability and the added-value of the proposed solution.
- Promoting the convergence toward common policies and interoperable technical solutions is another DIGOIDUNA recommendation addressed by ODIN.

Building on the DIGOIDUNA recommendations:

- In order to promote the convergence toward an integrated solution, ODIN should exploit institutional coordination and EC policy instruments, which should contribute to drive demand and foster trust around the PID infrastructure.
- Another aspect, which should be taken into account by the ODIN project is to identify funding schemes which are flexible enough to allow the reallocation of funds in the portfolio based on emerging requirements and needs.

Mobilizing resources

1. **Funding agencies should design funding schemes, which may attract new public and private investments and efforts in developing and adopting DI-based added value services and solutions.**
2. **Stakeholders, and especially funding agencies, should foster interoperability based on consolidation of established DI systems (where possible) more than on proliferation of ad hoc systems.**
3. **Actions should be taken to mobilize consolidated technical skills to implement effective digital identifiers infrastructures within SDIs and adopt measures to assess the quality and impact of them for the exploitation of e-Science results.**

In line with the third set of recommendations:

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- Following the “Don’t reinvent the wheel principle” claimed by DIGOIDUNA, ODIN aims to work on consolidated initiatives (e.g. DOI, ORCID) and promote their interoperability instead of introducing new solutions.
- ODIN embraces the recommendation from DIGOIDUNA of enlarging the demand of PID solutions and services by involving very different domains (e.g. HSS and HEP) and evangelizing domains, which usually don’t use PIDs.

Building on the DIGOIDUNA recommendations:

- As mentioned above, the institutional support is recognized by DIGOIDUNA as an essential aspect for the success of the infrastructure. Based on this idea, ODIN should exploit the DIGOIDUNA recommendation of rising institutional consensus around the issue of interoperability between data and contributors, and make funding initiatives in this context a priority in the political agenda at national and international level.
- The DIGOIDUNA guidelines suggest that actions should be taken to mobilize financial resources aiming at triggering a wider demand of usage of the proposed solution. Following this recommendation, ODIN should incentive funding schemes, which may attract investments from private and public sectors in order to diversify the sustainability of the initiative.
- Training and education are crucial aspects in the DIGOIDUNA recommendations to favour the mobilization of human resources. In line with this trajectory, ODIN should promote innovation in scholarship models and planning interventions to promote education activities aiming at expanding and reinforcing knowledge and skills.

Sustainable solutions

- 1. Stakeholders need to develop business models where the costs of developing and sustaining identifier infrastructures and the responsibility in granting the long term sustainability of these infrastructures are distributed among the beneficiaries.**
- 2. The flexibility of funding sources should be enhanced, allowing the reallocation of funds in the portfolio to enable the rapid scaling of promising solutions that embed or promote the value (usage) of identifiers.**
- 3. Funding bodies must support the development of collaborative models and actions to create synergies and exchange opportunities between the private/commercial sector and the scientific sector**

In line with the fourth set of recommendations:

- ODIN agrees on the DIGOIDUNA recommendation that sustainability is crucial for the success of the interoperability layer and depends on the value of services.
- Another view in line with the DIGOIDUNA recommendations is that funding models should support the local participation and access to emerging PID infrastructures.

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Building on the DIGOIDUNA recommendations:

- Based on the DIGOIDUNA results, flexible business and sustainability models should be included within the overall framework proposed by ODIN in order to facilitate the rapid reallocation of financial resources and the scaling of the proposed solutions and services.
- Stakeholder participation is largely promoted by ODIN and it should be extended (according the DIGOIDUNA approach) to the definition of sustainability plans in order to distribute the responsibility in ensuring the long-term sustainability of the infrastructure among the beneficiaries.
- The cross-fertilization and knowledge-sharing between academia and industry is another DIGOIDUNA recommendation which should be exploited by ODIN as a big opportunity to increase the potential of innovation in terms of ROI and create new synergies and opportunities between the private/commercial sector and the scientific sector.

In conclusion, our evaluation of the ODIN approach has shown an overall adherence to the DIGOIDUNA guidelines and principles. We have identified some aspects, especially at organizational and economical level, which can be further exploited in the second part of the project to develop an interoperability solution, which is sustainable, valuable, scalable and addressing the real needs of the relevant stakeholders.